

Post Modern Youth Sensibility in Chetan Bhagat's One Night @ the Call Center

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Abstract

The novel, One Night @ the Call Center explores the complexities of modern life and post modern youth sensibilities which are crushed under the impacts and exploitations in the age of globalization. The plot of the novel is an admixture of past memories and present realities. The story of the novel encapsulates the span of one night. It is the portrayal of six call center executives who are representatives of thousand of lives professionally confined to the globalized world of call center. Every character from the novel symbolically represents the anxieties and insecurities of the rising Indian middle class, including questions about career, inadequacy, marriage, and family conflicts in postmodern India. All the characters from the novel are in frustration for their unfulfilled aspirations and job insecurity.

Key words – Post Modern, Youth, Sensibility etc.

Introduction

Chetan Bhagat has established himself as one of the best novelists in the world. He has written six novels and two non –fictions which are best-seller like *Five Point Someone* (2004), *One Night @ the Call Centre*(2005), *The Three Mistakes of My Life* (2008), *2 States* (2009), and *Revolution 2020*(2011), *Half Girlfriend* (2014), and non-fiction *What Young India Wants* (2012) *One Indian Girl* (2016). Most of them are adopted in Bollywood movies. Indian youth, their despairs, hopes, aspiration, and their problems remained at the center of his every work. His work is not only a picture of the harsh reality of the youth in India but spiritual guidance, moral support, and technical suggestions also. The youth from different backgrounds with their ethos, aspirations, sentiments, and isolations in their life is the key concern of Chetan Bhagat's Novel. He has used the novel as a perfect tool to entertain, motivate and inspire the youth of 21st century India. His novels are nothing but a great projection of post modern youth sensibility.

The novel, *One Night @ the Call Center* explores the complexities of modern life and post modern youth sensibilities which are crushed under the impacts and exploitations in the age of globalization. The plot of the novel is an admixture of past memories and present realities. The story of the novel encapsulates the span of one night. It is the portrayal of six call center executives who are representatives of thousand of lives professionally confined to the globalized world of call center. All of them are working at Connexions in Gurgaon, Harayana. They have to answer American customers who have complaints against their home applications like refrigerators, ovens, vacuum cleaners, etc. They are facing the threat of job insecurity in the name of right-sizing, though their working hour's

odd and satisfy rude American customers. Thus professional and personal anxieties of the modern youths are key concerns of the novel.

Every character from the novel symbolically represents the anxieties and insecurities of the rising Indian middle class, including questions about career, inadequacy, marriage, and family conflicts in postmodern India. All the characters from the novel are in frustration for their unfulfilled aspirations and job insecurity.

The characters like Shyam Mehra, Priyanka, Varun Malhotra, Esha Singh, Radhika Jha, and Military Uncle are introduced by Chetan Bhagat in a distinguished way. Shyam Mehra, shortly called Sam Marcy, is intellectual and efficient but he lacks self-confidence. He wants to do B.Ed and join a School, but insufficient funds wedged him into his least interesting job at the call center. He pursues the post of team leader not because of his will for the high post but to marry Priyanka, whose mother wants a well-settled groom for her only daughter. Shyam, the protagonist of the novel, is not acknowledged in his family as he works in a call center whereas his cousins are doctors and engineers. On his cousin's marriage, nobody cares for him. Working at a call center is not a prestigious job for them. Shyam describes:

It wasn't surprising; I am only cared for so much.

Every cousin of mine is becoming a doctor or engineer.

You can say I am the black sheep of my family.

Though I do not think that expression is correct.

After all, what's wrong with the black sheep- don't people wear black sweaters?"

(*One Night @the Call Center* p-15)

So he considers himself as a black sheep of the family as he can't earn properly. Shyam represents 300000 BPO employees in India who are working day and night. They are treated as resources and not by their names or real names. The names that suit American accents are used for everyone. In W.H.Auden's words, they are 'Unknown Citizen' who is identified by their pseudo names or Id numbers.

Priyanka, a heroine of the novel who is an ex-girlfriend of Shyam, is introduced as an ultra-modern woman. She is sandwiched between her own aspirations and her mother's ambitious possessiveness. Chetan Bhagat portrays the female characters as ultra-modern women. They have two edges of choices; they want liberty and freedom at times, and at the same time they have to make their parents happy and compromise with their views. The same happens in the life of Priyanka; the female protagonist of the novel, who is Shyam's ex-girlfriend. After a long premarital affair, Priyanka breaks up with Shyam. But she is at sea, between her own aspirations and her mother's over-ambitious possessiveness. Circumstances force her to follow her mother's will as it is her intention also to keep her mother happy. So, she accepts to marry an NRI, who works 57 in Microsoft, whom she doesn't meet earlier, but she seems happy to get married to the NRI Mr. Microsoft. The happiness is not for her own sake as Ganesh is the right choice for her but it is to keep her mother happy, as Priyanka feels that her mother always thinks about her bright future. She confesses her love with Shyam but agrees to marry Ganesh just because her mother ponders over him as creditable husband material. She shares the good news with her colleagues but when notices the altered photo of the hiding bald of her fiancé, she rejected the marriage, and the love birds are reunited but have to wait for two years to marry as their career is their main priority.

Varun Malhotra is one most important characters in the novel. He is shortly called Vroom or agent Victor Mell. His pseudo name Vroom itself suggests that he is fond of speed and bikes or anything on wheels. Vroom has to earn money for maintaining a high standard with his friend circle. To ride a bike so fast is his own solution to get relaxed from stress. Shyam reveals his mental and physical condition,

"I couldn't sleep at all.

Just lay in bed all day and now I feel sick.

Need to get some energy back."

(ONCC, 21)

Vroom is representative of the modern youth of India who likes wearing branded clothes and shoes, joining clubs and night bars, smoking cigarettes, and using the internet excessively.

The face of urban fashionable girls in the novel is Esha Singh or agent Eliza Singer. She is the nice-looking and the most fashionable girl in the group. The narrator Shyam describes her;

"She is an ambitious girl who wants to become a model.

Her life represents the ambitious middle-class youth

who are running after blind race of materialism"[72].

She represents today's modern young girls who leave their homes for their passionate desires to become a model. Esha has joined a call center job to get a livelihood. She becomes mad about her passionate dream to become a model. Her ambition leads her even to lose her character and obliged to sleep with the forty year man to get the model opportunities. She feels guilty. She reveals to Shyam :

The guy I slept with- forty-year-old designer. —

He told my agent later I was too short to be

a ramp model.....and that son of a bitch sends

some cash as compensations afterward...||

She further says —

I hate myself, Shyam. I hate myself.

And I hate my face and the stupid mirror that shows me this face...

can I get my face altered? (142-143)

Radhika Jha, or agent Regina Jones is an only representative of a middle class married woman that works to support the family. She belongs to a joint family which is too traditional but Radhika accepts it for her love for her husband. She is torn between the modern culture and the traditional culture of her family. She tries to be an ideal wife and sacrifices herself for her husband and his family. But when she comes to know the decisive nature of her husband and takes a harsh decision which she herself has never expected so far that will happen in her life. Radhika decides to take divorce with Anuj and starts living with Esha

Conclusion

Thus, while depicting the life of call center employees, Chetan Bhagat has explored the harsh reality of Indian youth. Everyone has

his aspirations as well as problems also. These characters are the representative of the Indian young generation who wants to make their way in this age of competition. Metropolitan youth culture, cross-cultural issues, broken interpersonal relationships, rising individualism, condition of women, generation conflicts, and influence of foreign culture are the aspects touched by Chetan Bhagat.

References

1. Bhagat, Chetan. 2005 *One Night@ the Call Center*. New Delhi: Rupa & co.
2. Vaghela, Baldevbhai M.2004, "*Thematic Studies of Chetan Bhagat's Novels*", Paradise publication, Las Vegas.
3. Jadhav, Arvind. —*Representing Metropolitan Youth Culture: An assessment of Chetan Bhagat's Five Point Someone and One Night @ the Call Center*|| The Criterion: An International Journal in English Vol.3.2 (2012): (1- 5).
4. <https://www.audible.com/author/Chetan-Bhagat/B001IQWOKY>
<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/jspui/bitstream/10603/251130/7/chapter-pdfhttps://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/isolation>
5. <http://ijellh.com/OJS/index.php/OJS/article/view/869/869>